

Recommended citation: Jolly, A. (2018). Informational skills as one of the learning outcomes in education of engineers. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 913-919). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672734.

Informational skills as one of the learning outcomes in education of engineers

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Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Philosophy & Purpose of Engineering Education

Keywords: Information, skill, accreditation, fake news

INTRODUCTION

Evaluation and accreditation of Higher Education Institutions takes into account more and more criteria that were not considered 10 years ago, they are mostly arising from learning outcomes approaches. The institutions need to provide expected learning outcomes linked to programs in relation to the needs of society and must be also able to explain how they evaluate them in relation to their educational process.

In engineering education, it is the case for national agencies such as CTI (Commission des Titres d'Ingénieur) as well as for European labels such as EUR Ace, proposed by ENAEE, both agencies including professional members which ensures that those learning outcomes are linked to professional ones. Those agencies have proposed lists of skills that should be those of graduated students, among these skills, many soft skills are present besides technical ones.

When CTI revised its accreditation criteria in 2016, as all agencies accredited by ENQA, it had to consult stakeholders about its new standards. For this occasion, CDEFI (Conférence des Directeurs des Ecoles Françaises d'Ingénieur) asked that among the 14 learning outcomes considered as mandatory for an engineer, one could be about Informational skills because the companies employing engineers were complaining on the fact that during

internships and projects, students were unable to choose pertinent information among the huge flow of information they had at disposal. Some students and teachers are always thinking that it is only a technical problem linked with computer science approach!

Finding the good information is not only a problem of librarians, it needs critical spirit too. At the time when "Fake news" become a real problem event in politics, how teach future engineers the good way to fetch and select information?

This will be discussed in the paper with reference to the work already done by several networks of institutions in France and abroad. This is a great issue for our engineers graduated at master level: critical spirit being a strong point in their education.

1 WHAT ARE INFORMATIONAL SKILLS

1.1 As defined by CTI and ABDU (Association of Deans of university libraries)

CTI [1] defines, among the 14 skills necessary for engineers, informational skills as the ability to find relevant information, evaluate and exploit it. This is a rather broad definition that can apply in many fields, not only scientific ones and that can be evaluated through many different activities.

The definition lies within the ideas developed by ABDU [2] for French "Conférence des Présidents d'Université" considering that information is a priority at the 21th century and that it will also play a strong role in long life learning. Its referential is based on 4 great principles allowing students to really master information, those are:

- capacity to identify a need for information and define its nature and its extend
- being able to access efficiently to the necessary information
- being able to evaluate in a critical way the information obtained (sources, demarches and results)
- being able to product and communicate from the result on the research of information

In both contexts the idea of engineering is not very present, so it is interesting to turn to the point of view of a French institution dedicated to education of engineers INSA (Institut National des Sciences Appliquées in Lyon) that has dedicated much energy on those subjects.

1.2 As considered by INSA

INSA took advantage of its association of alumni to define the skills needed in this domain [3] in 2015. It is interesting to notice that this investigation met a good success among engineers, concerning a large spectrum of jobs such as engineering study, project responsible, research engineers. 25% of the answering engineers declaring they have informational skill in their job description.

The difficulties encountered in front of information depend very much of the kind of job occupied:

- For engineering study, the difficulty is to know the fitted resources and to be sure to get exhaustively the results
- For research engineers, the difficulty was to be able to face the huge amount of information and to capitalise and memorise the results of the researches

- For responsible of production, the major difficulty was to face the huge amount of information
- For specialised engineers, the difficulty is to formulate the good questions and to capitalise and memorise the results
- For quality engineers, the problem was to know and access to fitted resources

We see that previous skills are formulated here in a more precise and applied way, but that the great challenges for information defined in 1.1 remain valid also for engineers.

1.3 As considered worldwide

Canadian and Belgium universities have worked since a long time on those subjects.

Canadian experts [4] define informational skills as the set of abilities allowing people to determine the times when they need information, and then to find, evaluate and use this information. This can be developed in 5 essential skills:

- Being able to distinguish the extent of information needed
- Being able to access this information in an effective and efficient way
- Being able to realise a critical evaluation of the information and of its sources, and to integrate it in its network of knowledge
- Being able to use information efficiently to reach a specific aim
- Being able to understand economic legal and social questions surrounding the use of information, so as to use information in an ethical and legal way

They constructed a norm on information skills in higher education and 22 indicators allow to measure the mastery of information that the student acquire. We notice than those fields are not significantly different from CTI's choices.

In Belgium and Australia [6] too, this field has also been widely studied and books have even been published. We must notice that Belgian people even think of a minimum level in this skill to enter higher education [5] because success of students in university reveals to be very in link with their level in informational skills.

2 WHAT ARE THE STAKES OF INFORMATIONAL SKILLS?

2.1 Fake news

Since the terrorist attacks of 2015, this word is very much used for political reasons, and in our everyday life especially through internet, we are invaded by those unverified information, that very often, young people take as true ones, because they are broadcasted.

So the interest of the world of engineering education for this phenomena is completely understandable because many engineering skills are in link with society and its bad understanding make students misunderstand the economic or politic context of their own work. Furthermore, on those fields that are highly delicate ones, the acquisition of reflex and methods got on scientific fields is easier and give rise to less debates than heuristic one.

It cannot be the only duty of higher education, but families must also prepare their children to this aspect of things, however, we want to diversify the social origins of our students, and this is not evident for all social classes: equality of chances also lies on this good apprehension of all kinds of information sources.

2.2 Scientific information

The French ministry is particularly preoccupied [7] on those aspects, there is a real need for citizen to come back to scientific facts, the link between science and society is a major challenge not only concerning public information on scientific matters but also for the access to science to define projects, politics without opinions or beliefs but on very factual elements.

There is a real need to inspire from a structured scientific demarche for questioning the “ready to think” and stimulate critical thinking

2.3 Information necessary for real life or companies

Since several years we have complaints from our industrial partners on the fact that students-engineers are not able to find the pertinent information any more, this is a real problem because companies have less time to innovate and very often, they take an interneer to launch an innovation process. In this case it is very important that the information got be of good quality because the future work of the company can be based on that information.

Very often this skill is transdisciplinary and preparing our students to look besides their usual and comfortable field [8]; at the beginning this kind of teaching was given by librarian in specific teachings, nowadays those teachings are backed to technical apprentice ships with active pedagogies.

3 HOW TO TEACH INFORMATIONAL SKILLS SO AS TO EVALUATE THEM - ONE EXAMPLE

3.1 The work done in INSA Lyon

There are rather few indications on how get the informational skills in pedagogical books but INSA Lyon [9] realised a good work on informational skills, it can be considered as a basis for all education system.

This work lasted from 2014 to 2016, one of the major point that launched this demarche was the fact that technical teachers criticized the previous classical teachings on information, insured only by librarians, then it was decided to work in teams of teachers and librarians using opinions of students and engineers (see before). Students asked for a more contextualised teaching, and preferred teachings included in multidisciplinary projects.

A discovery trail has been launched in 2016, under the form of exercises; the principles underlying this creation were:

- limit information to basic informational skills so as not to make the exercise too dense
- autonomous work
- more interaction between students and teachers

This discovery trail has been successful; however, all students were not convinced of the importance to know the resources of the library.

3.2 The global training repository

The approach taken was a programme approach: expected learning outcomes of the graduates were used; 9 learning outcomes were used, the more important being:

- matching needs and resources,
- which includes: sort sources,
- use sources,
- sort results

This is fully consistent with both requirements of CTI and ABDU.

A progression of apprenticeship was necessary because informational skills must be evaluated all along the curriculum.

For the 3 first years (undergraduate students), first aims of apprenticeship were described, then evaluation criteria, followed by assessment and learning situations. Each year, students will work specifically on one of the skills and be evaluated on this skill. At the same time, the other skills will be only recalled.

-during the first year (after A level), students live the discovery trail: the skills aimed is then to be able to know and use the resources necessary for studies: the students can take them into account and criticise their previous uses. Those theoretical knowledge including critical one (Google, Wikipedia) are the module “numerical tools, documentary research”, it is an exercise sequence and gives rise to a multiple choice questionnaire. The pedagogy is an active one with teams of 4 students made at random.

-during the second year, the aim is to be able to find and evaluate the results of these information researches in relation with a project or a problematic, students learn to define external criteria for the validation of information; the theoretical contributions are: what is evaluation, which intents, which issues. The pedagogy is on the form of a multidisciplinary project; during the first part of the sequence, students use voting boxes for a formative evaluation with gaming elements, then the projects in small teams take place with documentary researches and methodological tutorials, then a practical work follow where student build a grid of criteria for the information concerning their project.

-during the third year, the aim is to be able to delimit precisely the needs for information for a project thanks to a mental card, to produce and communicate, to manage information, to create a toolbox “information management” and a bibliographic database. The theoretical knowledge are bibliography tools, mind mapping software, issues on plagiarism. During these exercise students are realising multidisciplinary projects in groups of 2 to 8 students, the evaluation is realised through a report where bibliographic references are evaluated.

In some cases, the evaluation is realised by disciplinary teachers, that are taught on information, on bibliographic norms and non-plagiarism in reports.

For the moments the modules for the 4th and 5th year (Master degree) are not completely defined, preliminary reflexion decided that the aim would be the ability to know and use

resources for research and for companies, it could be done within projects, with self-evaluations.

4 CONCLUSION

The debate concerning information skills has not yet convinced all institutions; though this new criterion appeared in 2016, we see very few information on those skills in the self-evaluation reports; the only example publicised in France is the one presented before.

The teachers of INSA themselves think that things could be improved for example by gamification [10] of some sequences but also being more creative for the evaluation of some sequences thanks to cooperation with other institutions.

Librarians had to get new skills for supervision, apprenticeship of new tools; but they had also to change their professional identities becoming much more a teacher that has to evaluate. This is sometimes difficult as for all changes but the dynamism of the team is to be kept!

We think that the central point is the constitution of multidisciplinary teams of teachers because disciplinary teachers do not know what librarians know and sharing knowledge could be a good help for them because teachers are also researchers and that knowledge on information could help in their own practice, on the contrary discussion between disciplinary scientist and librarians could make those discover new fields of activities.

It is very surprising for CTI that apart from INSA we have not in our evaluations discovered other institutions that had a reflection on this skill which is a fundamental one, moreover there is not one unique way to treat the problem, agile methods for example could be another way.

But, as what happened for sustainable development criteria, we know it takes time so that a new skill is taken into account especially in transdisciplinary fields so we hope that this kind of paper will make institutions reflect on the subject: too often this subject is considered by scientific teachers only as the problem of librarians alone!

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